

Latin Suffixes in Medical Terminology

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Abstract: The article provides examples of lexical and grammatical features of the word-formation suffix, which forms various meanings in the Latin language. Terms with this suffix are a minority in medical terminology. These suffixes are added to the root of the word and have different meanings. Latin has suffixes forming nouns and suffixes forming adjectives, knowledge of suffixes forming a word or meaning is important for easy compilation and translation of medical terms.

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In Latin, suffixes are widely used in the creation of medical, anatomical and clinical terms. Suffixes are endings that are not used independently, but serve to express various meanings related to lexical and grammatical properties, joining the root. The derived base obtained in this way is called suffixal. Suffixes serve as an important classification. As a word-formation basis, various categories of words are used in suffixation - noun, adjective and verb. Some suffixes are added only with the root of a certain number of words: For example, suffixes **al-**, **ar** with the root of a noun; suffixes **-io**, **-or** with the root of a verb. The addition of a suffix starting with a consonant letter to the root of the word occurs through an auxiliary vowel. This is called an interference. Latin words usually come with the vowel- **i** - and in words borrowed from greek with **-o**. For example, lat. **cruc-i-formis** - cruciform; **tuberos** – **i-tas**- tuberosity; greek. **bronch-o-** genus - bronchogenic, etc.

When forming adjectives, the suffix is attached to the root of the noun, in which it is in the form of the genitive singular. For example: **larynx**, **ngis** – **laryng-e-us**; **margo**, **inis** - **margin-al-is**; **cartilago**, **inis** – **cartilagin-e-us**; **occiput**, **itis** – **occipit-al-is** etc.

Terms with broad meanings are created using word-formation elements. Below we will look at the suffixes that are added to the root of the word and create new meanings.

I. Nouns formed by a suffix meaning diminutive meanings: 1) **-ul**, for example: **lobus**, **lob-ulus** – lobe, lobule; **vena**, **ven-ula**- vein, venule; **lingua**, **ling-ula** - tongue, tongue; **frenum**, **fren-ulum** – bridle; **caput**, **capit-ulum** - head; **tuba**, **tub-ulus** - tube, tubule; **nodus**, **nod-ulus**-node, nodule, **globus**, **glob-ulus** - globe; **membrana**, **membran-ula** -membrane, membranule; **glomus**, **glomer-ulum** – tangle, ; **vesica**, **vesic-ula** – bladder, vesicle; **ductus**, **duct-ulus** - duct; **fossa**, **foss-ula** - pit, dimple.

2) **-cul**, **canalis**, **canali-culus**- canal, canaliculus; **os**, **ossi-culum**-bone; **auris**, **auri** – **cula**-ear; **cutis**, **cuti-cula**-skin, cuticle; **tuber**, **tuber-culum**- tubercle; **venter**, **ventri -culus**- stomach, ventricle; **genu**, **geni** - **culum**- knee; **radix**, **radi** – **cula**- root, radical; **corpus**, **corpus-culum**-body, corpuscle; **dens**, **denti-culus** – tooth, denticle; **vas**, **vas-culum**- vessel, small vessel.

3) **-ol**, area, are-**ola**- area, areola; bronchus, bronchi-**olus**- bronchus, bronchiole; arteria, arteri-**ola**- artery, arteriole; fovea, fove-**ola** - pit, dimple. Nouns with these meanings are 4.

4) **-ell**, cerebrum, cereb-**ellum** - brain, cerebellum; lamina, lam-**ella**- lamella; Such nouns are 2.

5) **-ill**, mamma, mamm – **illa**- mammary gland, mamilla;

II. Suffixes of nouns from a verb expressing the meaning of an action, process:

1)-**io** (*tio, sio, xio*) flexum, flex-**io**- to flex, flexion. In Latin, such nouns denote operations, methods of examination, treatment, and physiological functions. For example: operatum, operat-**io**-to operate, operation, surgical intervention; palpatum, palpat-**io**- to palpate, palpation; emotum, emot-**io**- to feel, emotion, feeling; curatum, curat-**io**- to treat, treatment; lectum, lect-**io**-lecture; auscultatum, auscultat-**io**- auscultation, hearing; percussum, percuss-**io**-percussion, knocking etc.

2)-**or** (*tor, sor, xor*) constrictum, m. constrict-**or** - constrict, constrictive muscle; depressum, m. depress-**or** - lower, sinking muscle; excavatum, excavat-**or** -excavate, excavator; extensum, m. extens-**or** – extension, extensor muscle; tensum, m. tens-**or**- to strain, a straining muscle; curatum, curat-**or** – to take care, curator, supervisor; repetetum, repetit-**or** -to repeat, tutor. Such nouns denote an object, an instrument, and activities in various fields.

III. Nouns that form from a verb expressing the result of an action:

1)-**ura** (*tura, sura, xura*) curvatum, curvat-**ura**– bend, curvature; fractum, fract-**ura**– break, fracture; sutum, sut-**ura** –suture, seam; fissum, fiss-**ura**-crack, fissure; comissum, commiss-**ura**– commission; junctum, junct-**ura**–to bind, juncture; incisum, incis-**ura** - to cut, tenderloin, etc.

IV. Suffixes of adjectives derived from a noun:

1) **-os** (*us, a, um*) squama, squam-**osus**-scales, scaly; fibra, fibr-**osus** – fiber, fibrous; infectio, infecti-**osus** - infection, infectious; cavern, cavern-**osus** – cave, cavernous, porous; spina, spin-**osus** – awn, spinous, etc.

1)-**ic** (*us, a, um*) thorax, thorac-**icus** – thorax, thoracic; zygoma, zygomat-**icus** -cheekbone, zygomatic; gaster, gastr-**icus** - stomach, gastric;

3) **-in** (*us, a, um*) palatum, palat-**inus** - palate, palatal; uterus, uter-**inus**- uterus, uterine;

4) **-e** (*us, a, um*) oesophagus, oesophag-**eus** - esophagus, esophageal; os, oss-**eus**-bone, bony, osseous; perone, peron-**eus** - small tibia; larynx, laryng-**eus** - larynx, laryngeal; pharynx, pharyng – **eus** - pharyngeal;

VI. Adverbs forming an adjective from a noun meaning similarity:

1) **-ide** (*us, a, um*) rhombos, rhombo-**ideus** - rhombus, rhomboid; delta, delto-**ideus** - deltoid; pterygo, pterygo-**ideus** -pterygo-id, wing-shaped; xypho, xypho-**ideus**–sword, xiphoid; thyro – thyro-**ideus** – shield, thyroid; stylo, stylo-**ideus** - awl, awl-shaped, etc.

2) **-form** (*is, e*) crux, cruci – **formis** - cross, cruciform; pisum, pisi –**formis** - pea, pea-shaped; pimum, piri-**formis** - pear, pear-shaped, etc.

3)-**at** (*us, a, um*) arcus, arcu-**atus** – arc, arc-shaped; luna, lun-**atus** - moon, semilunar;

VII. An adjective forming a suffix from a noun meaning a carrier:

-fer –(**a, um**) semen, semini-**fer** -seed, seminal; sudor, sudori – **fer** - sweat, sweaty;

VIII. An adverb forming an adjective from a noun meaning a derivative, origin:

-gen (*us, a, um*) cancer, cancro – **genus** – cancer, causing cancer; pyo, pyo –**genus** – pus,

causing pus, etc

At a conclusion, we can say that Latin suffixes increase the vocabulary of the Latin language, since they are added to the root of the word and acquire a new meaning.

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